

Automotive RADAR Planar Antenna Optimization Based on Conformal Transformation Optics

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Abstract—A novel approach to mitigate diffraction effects from finite ground planes in antenna design is presented. The method is based on conformal transformation optics. A computational framework has been developed to optimize the shape of the ground plane since it has a great impact on the beam ripple and width of the radiation pattern of an antenna. Due to the limited thickness of the outer wall of slotted waveguide antennas, it is not possible to shape this outer wall, which acts as the ground plane of the antenna. Conformal transformation optics presents a solution to virtually add a deformation without needing to change the physical shape of the ground plane. Although conformal transformation optics can also be applied to transverse-magnetic waves, large fluctuations in the dielectric constant with respect to the wavelength cannot be supported in practice. In order to mitigate this problem, we have proposed a rescaling of the dielectric constant. Furthermore, we derive the connection between conformal transformation optics and transverse electromagnetic modes, which serve as a tool for joint optimization of the radiation pattern together with the conformal transformation. This method is then used to optimize the radiation pattern of a slot antenna and evaluated for increasing curvature within the conformal transformation.

Numerical computations have shown promising results, i.e. a reduction of the farfield ripple from 1.92 dB to 0.64 dB at a half-power beam-width of 112° at 77 GHz. This is a promising result for designing automotive radars with a wide field of view, especially, for advanced driver-assistance systems used in the corner radars. This will contribute to further improving safety on the roads.

Index Terms—Radar antennas, Conformal mapping, Slot antennas, Meta-materials.

I. INTRODUCTION

Safety on the road is a primordial focus for vehicles whether they are autonomous or not. Automotive radars operating at the millimeter waves (mmWaves) are key technologies enabling advanced driver-assistance systems like automated emergency braking, forward collision warning, and blind spot detection to name a few. With the aim to reduce accidents on the roads further, these technologies will need to be improved.

The introduction of transformation optics [1], allows shaping the electromagnetic propagation in order to improve the performance of electromagnetic devices. A coordinate transformation is applied within a domain of interest, which modifies the material properties of the device. Typically, the resulting material properties can not be found in nature and are thus created by engineered metamaterials. The basic structure of the metamaterials needs to be smaller than the wavelength in order to mimic the desired material properties. At mmWave

frequencies, metallic structures are difficult to manufacture with high precision and in large volumes. Conformal transformation optics (CTO) offers an appealing solution to this problem. Indeed, the dielectric properties resulting from these transformations are locally isotropic and can be made from materials where only the dielectric constant needs to be designed. If the dielectric constant remains above unity, these metamaterials can be manufactured using 3D printing [2] or CNC-milled plastic [3].

However, the CTO does not guarantee that the dielectric constant will be above unity in all places. For certain devices, these areas can simply be removed since little energy passes through these areas. Therefore the performance is not compromised such as in [3]. In other devices, these areas play an important role in the operation of the device. For such devices, [4] has introduced a rescaling method that limits the values of the dielectric constants without affecting the operation of the device. This method can eliminate the dielectric constants below unity and reduce the maximum dielectric constant within target areas in the device.

This paper introduces a modified rescaling method, which further reduces the dielectric constants in the target areas of the CTO-designed material. To validate this method, optimization is performed for wide-beam automotive radar antennas. This optimization aims to minimize the ripple on the radiation pattern while keeping a wide beamwidth. This ripple results from traveling waves along the ground plane, which diffract from the edge of the finite ground plane. The ripple reduces the detectable range of the radar system. Furthermore, the ripple also induces a phase variation in the pattern. When the ripples are different between elements of the radar array, ambiguity is added to the angle of arrival detection. To mitigate these problems, a deformed ground plane is designed by implementing a CTO-based optimization algorithm. This method acts as a demonstration for the use of CTO to optimize the radiation pattern, this will be extended in the future to optimize the radiation of common antenna technologies.

II. CONFORMAL TRANSFORMATION OPTICS

The conformal transformation optics (CTO) in this design is based on the coordinate transformation between a reference- and physical domain. Let the coordinates (x, y) in the physical domain, and the coordinates (u, v) in the reference domain be given. Then, a set of complex variables can be defined as $Z = x + iy$ and $W = u + iv$. Then the operators (matrices)

Fig. 1. Boundary conditions for TEM-mode inside an arbitrary quadrilateral

representing a transformation between the two domains can be denoted as $Z(W)$ and $W(Z)$, i.e., direct and reverse transformations, respectively. The CTO defines the coordinate transformation between the reference and physical domains $Z(W)$ via the permittivity and permeability tensors required to implement the coordinate transformation [5]

$$\epsilon_Z = \frac{\mathbf{J}\epsilon_W\mathbf{J}^T}{\det(\mathbf{J})}, \quad \mu_Z = \frac{\mathbf{J}\mu_W\mathbf{J}^T}{\det(\mathbf{J})}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_Z, μ_Z , and ϵ_W, μ_W are the permittivity and permeability tensors in the physical and reference space respectively. \mathbf{J} is the Jacobian of the coordinate transformation $Z(W)$. When the transformations are constraint to strictly conformal transformations, the Jacobian satisfies the following identity

$$\frac{\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^T}{\det(\mathbf{J})} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

This is a direct result of applying the Cauchy-Riemann equations on \mathbf{J} , which are satisfied by all conformal transformations (mappings). Moreover, a solution to the Cauchy-Riemann equations also satisfies Laplace's equation, which is used to compute the conformal coordinate transformation. Typically this type of conformal transformation is used for transverse electric (TE) propagation in the (x, y) -plane since this is only affected by the ϵ_{zz} component. Hence, the implementation can be performed by only changing the permittivity $\epsilon_r = \epsilon_{zz}$. Similarly, the transverse magnetic (TM) propagation is only affected by μ_{zz} . The transformation based on the permeability can be converted to the permittivity via the refractive index

$$n(x, y) = \sqrt{\epsilon_r(x, y)_{\mu_r=1}} = \sqrt{\mu_r(x, y)_{\epsilon_r=1}}. \quad (3)$$

However, the permittivity should not change significantly with respect to the wavelength to maintain the same operation of the transformation.

A. Conformal modulus and characteristic impedance

Unfortunately, not all coordinate transformations within arbitrary domains can be conformal. This is why a parameter known as the conformal modulus can be used in order to ensure that the CTO works. It has been shown in [6] that

a conformal coordinate transformation between two quadrilaterals exists when they share the same conformal modulus M . A physical interpretation is provided between the equivalence of the conformal modulus and the resistance of a thin metal plate with homogeneous resistivity. In this paper, we propose an analogous analysis to connect M to the characteristic impedance of a transverse electromagnetic (TEM) mode. To do this, let us consider the domain from Fig. 1 With the corresponding boundary conditions to compute the TEM-mode. The current flow on the top or bottom conductor is given by

$$I = \oint_C \mathbf{H} \cdot d\mathbf{l}, \quad (4)$$

where the line C encloses one of the conductors of the transmission line (see Fig. 1). Assuming a homogeneous background material

$$I = \int_{x_{\min}}^{x_{\max}} \frac{1}{Z_0} \hat{z} \times \hat{\mathbf{E}} \cdot d\mathbf{x} = \int_{x_{\min}}^{x_{\max}} \frac{1}{Z_0} \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} dx, \quad (5)$$

where Z_0 is the free space wave impedance. Following the analysis in Section 2.2 of [6]

$$\int_{x_{\min}}^{x_{\max}} \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} dx = \frac{1}{M} (V_{\max} - V_{\min}). \quad (6)$$

Recalling that the characteristic impedance is computed as

$$Z_{TEM} = \frac{V_{\max} - V_{\min}}{I}, \quad (7)$$

where V_{\max} and V_{\min} are the potentials at the upper and the lower conductors, respectively, i.e., the boundary values. Now, combining (5), (6) and (7) we arrive at an expression for the conformal modulus

$$M = \frac{Z_{TEM}}{Z_0}, \quad (8)$$

In this way, we have shown that the conformal modulus of a quadrilateral shape, can be computed from the TEM-mode inside that domain. This allows us to optimize for the conformal modulus within the same EM-simulation tool where the radiation of our device is optimized. Lastly, the electric field $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ of a TEM-mode

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}} = -\nabla V, \quad (9)$$

where V is the electrostatic potential. V can be found solving Laplace's equation in the same way that the v -coordinates are obtained from the conformal transformation explained above. We aim to exploit this duality by setting the boundary values V_{\min} and V_{\max} to $\min\{v\}$ and $\max\{v\}$, respectively. Hence, the electrostatic potential has the same solution as the v -coordinate of the coordinate transformation. This can be used to relate $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ of the TEM-mode to ϵ_r of the conformal transformation since

$$\epsilon_r = \epsilon_{zz} = \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 = |\nabla v|^2 = |\nabla V|^2 = |\hat{\mathbf{E}}|^2. \quad (10)$$

III. OPTICAL PATH RESCALING

As has been shown in [4], it is possible to rescale the dielectric constants resulting from applying CTO. This can be used to avoid areas where $\epsilon_r < 1$, which allows plastic-based implementations. Furthermore, it was shown in [4] that this method can be used to reduce the maximum dielectric constant ϵ_r^{\max} . As mentioned in section II, ϵ_r should not change significantly with respect to the wavelength. Unfortunately, this is difficult to maintain while achieving a meaningful transformation within the array spacing which is typical for automotive radars. Therefore, a rescaling method is used to reduce the permittivity to maintain the correct propagation of the TM wave.

A. Figure of merit for general conformal transformations

With the aim to eliminate $\epsilon_r < 1$ using the rescaling method, a figure of merit FOM_ϵ is introduced next. The aim of this figure of merit is to set the maximum achievable permittivity after rescaling, for a given conformal transformation. Since this maximum will be achieved when the minimum and maximum permittivity fall on the same phase-front,

$$\text{FOM}_\epsilon = \frac{\max\{\epsilon_r\}}{\min\{\epsilon_r\}} \geq \max\{\epsilon_{res}\}, \quad (11)$$

where the minimum and maximum are taken over the entire transformation domain and ϵ_{res} are the permittivity values after rescaling. Although FOM_ϵ is not necessarily equal to $\max\{\epsilon_{res}\}$, it will indicate the upper bound without having to perform the rescaling method itself. Furthermore, FOM_ϵ can be computed using (10). Thus it is possible to constraint the optimization to satisfy for both conformality and maximum permittivity at the same time.

B. Modified rescaling method for TM propagation

In the original rescaling method, the total length of the optical path is maintained to ensure the same operation of the device. For antennas, the absolute phase of the radiated elements can typically be arbitrary. Thus the total length of the optical path may be changed without changing the operation of this device. By relaxing this constraint, a new rescaling method is presented with the rescaled dielectric constant

$$\epsilon_{res}(x, y) = \frac{\mu_r(x, y)}{\min\{\mu_r(\Phi(x, y))\}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mu_r(\Phi(x, y))$ is the permeability along the phase-front Φ passing through the point (x, y) . When the coordinate transformation between (u, v) and (x, y) is computed, the phase-front can be found from the u - and v - coordinates in the reference space. Computing the phase-front in this way does not require the simulation in the physical domain using the non-rescaled values of $\mu_r(x, y)$. With this rescaling function, permittivity values below unity are rescaled to above unity. Moreover, if all permittivity values along a given phase-front are above unity, this rescaling function also minimizes these values.

Fig. 2. Reference and physical space for the conformal transformation. With equal radiation boundary.

Fig. 3. Reference space with the optimized ground plane for minimal ripple with the curvature constraint Δy_{\max} .

IV. DESIGN APPROACH

Fig. 2 shows the reference and physical spaces for the conformal transformation. As a radiating element, a slot in the ground plane was added with a width smaller than $\lambda_0/100$ which mimics an isotropic radiator in 2D. To ensure the same radiation from both spaces, the coordinate systems in both spaces should line up at the radiation boundaries. To achieve this, the curvature of the ground plane, near the side boundaries should go to zero. For the physical space, a ground plane of $1.9\lambda_0$ was chosen. This choice was made since it represents the 'worst case' ripple which is caused by the diffraction at the edges of a finite ground plane. This chosen size is also in the same order as the array spacing which can be typically found for automotive radars.

A. Optimized ground plane

To optimize the ground plane, various basis functions have been tested to optimize the ripple on the farfield pattern along the azimuth plane. The resulting ground plane curve is shown in Fig. 3. It was found that rescaling this curve based on Δy controls the ripple on the pattern. Since Δy also determines the curvature of the boundary from the transformation domain, it will control FOM_ϵ too. Therefore, Δy was swept to investigate the performance of the CTO-ground plane with respect to the dielectric properties.

Fig. 4. Permittivity distribution from the conformal transformation for the maximum curvature with $\Delta y_{\max} = 0.05$

B. Conformal mappings

After finding the shape of the deformed ground plane, the conformal mapping has been computed using COMSOL. This was done by solving Laplace's equation in the reference domain shown in Fig. 3. For the x - coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -w/2 \text{ on left boundary} \\ x &= w/2 \text{ on right boundary} \\ \frac{\partial x}{\partial n} &= 0 \text{ on top and bottom boundaries} \\ \nabla^2 x &= 0 \text{ inside the domain} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{n} is normal to the given boundary. For the y - coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} y &= 0 \text{ on top boundary} \\ y &= h \text{ on top boundary} \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} &= 0 \text{ on left and right boundaries} \\ \nabla^2 y &= 0 \text{ inside the domain} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

When $x(u, v)$ and $y(u, v)$ are known, $\mu_r = \mu_{zz}$ can be computed from (1) to implement the CTO. From this point on, we will refer to the implementation using μ_r as the 'direct transformation'. Furthermore, an implementation where the permeability is converted to the permittivity $\epsilon_r = \mu_r$ will be evaluated using (2). Lastly, the implementation in the permittivity with the proposed rescaling method using (12) is applied. The resulting permittivity distribution has been shown in Fig. 4 for the largest Δy_{\max} . Before rescaling is applied, $0.43 < \epsilon_r < 8.97$, after rescaling $1.00 < \epsilon_r < 3.23$

V. RESULTS

In Fig 5, the normalized radiation patterns are shown of the curved ground plane for different limits of the curvature constraint Δy_{\max} . Fig. 5(a) shows the radiation pattern of the optimize reference space from Fig. 3. It can be seen that the higher limit of Δy_{\max} results in a larger reduction of the ripple. Fig. 5(b) shows the radiation pattern in the physical space, with the conformal transformation directly

Fig. 5. Normalized azimuth patterns for different implementation of the curved ground plane, with different constraints on the curvature of the ground plane.

implemented in the permittivity. Comparing Fig 5(a) to Fig 5(b) demonstrates the problem with the direct conversion from permeability to permittivity. Fig. 5(c) however is implemented using the rescaled permittivity following (12). From this result, it can be seen that the rescaling function reduces this conversion error and brings the radiation pattern closer to the optimized result.

A. Figure of merit

Although Δy_{\max} gives an indication of the curvature of the conformal transformation, FOM_ϵ is directly related to μ_r . Moreover, FOM_ϵ gives the maximum possible permittivity necessary to implement the transformation after rescaling. For these reasons, the performance of the ground plane deformation has been evaluated in terms of FOM_ϵ . Fig. 6 shows FOM_ϵ as a function of Δy_{\max} .

B. Evaluation of ripple minimization

Since the transformation is designed with the aim to reduce the ripple on the radiation pattern, Fig. 7 shows this as a function of FOM_ϵ . It can be seen that higher values of FOM_ϵ allow for better optimization and a reduced ripple. Furthermore, the direct transformation follows the optimization result closely, confirming the operation of the conformal transformation. It can be seen that the permittivity-based implementation does not closely follow the optimization result. However, the rescaling function reduces this effect.

C. General evaluation

To validate that this approach is not only valid for the optimization of the ripple, a direct comparison is also made

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the figure of merit for the curvature of the conformal transformation, compared to the design constraint Δy

Fig. 7. Farfield ripple in the azimuth plane as a function of the FOM of the conformal transformation.

between the optimized farfield and the different implementations of the conformal transformation. Fig. 8 shows the RMSE of the different implementations. For each implementation, the optimization result (from Fig. 5(a)) is taken as the reference since this is what we aim to reproduce with this CTO device. The direct transformation performs best because it does not suffer from the permeability conversion. The error in the permittivity-based implementation without rescaling grows with the curvature of the transformation. This general comparison also shows that the rescaling function can be used to minimize the permeability conversion error.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated the use of conformal transformation optics (CTO) for the optimization of the radiation pattern of planar antennas. A design is demonstrated that can serve as a guide for the optimization of planar antenna elements for applications such as automotive radars with elements sizes in the order of one wavelength. A modified rescaling method has been proposed that minimizes the conversion error from permeability to permittivity resulting

Fig. 8. Error of the farfield patterns within the HPBW of the antenna.

from the application of CTO to TM-polarized waves. This method has been validated for varying levels of curvature in the coordinate transformation. Also, we have derived a relationship between the conformal modulus of a conformal transformation based on quadrilaterals and the characteristic mode of a TEM-mode. This allows for joint optimization of the electrical performance and the dielectric properties of the CTO device within commercial software.

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